

Spectral and biological properties of unsymmetrical imine complexes of dioxomolybdenum(VI) with sulfadrug azomethines and thiosemicarbazone

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A few unsymmetrical imine dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of the type $\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}')$ with thiophene thiosemicarbazone (LH) and sulfadruugs azomethines (L'H) have been synthesized in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The ligands are found to be monobasic bidentate and the complexes are diamagnetic. The ligands and the metal complexes have been screened against several bacteria and fungi.

Heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones as well as their metal complexes possess various biological activities¹. These compounds are emerging as a new class of experimental anticancer chemotherapeutic agents². Sulfadruugs have long been used against various diseases³. Owing to the wide range of medicinal properties of sulfadruugs and thiosemicarbazones and their ability to form chelates with the metal ions, we undertook the synthesis of unsymmetrical dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with bidentate monobasic ligands and screened them for their antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Results and discussion

The reactions of dioxobis(2,4-pentanedionato)-molybdenum(VI) with unsymmetrical ligands thiophenethiosemicarbazone (LH) and 2-acetylnaphthalene sulfapyridine, 2-acetylthiophene sulfapyridine, thiophene-2-carbaldehyde sulfapyridine, 2-fluorobenzaldehyde sulfapyridine, 2-acetylnaphthalene sulfaguanidine and 2-acetylthiophene sulfaguanidine (L'H) have been carried out in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry methanol. The reaction proceeds with the liberation of two molecules of 2,4-pentanedione. The resulting brown coloured solids are soluble in methanol, DMF and DMSO. The complexes are monomeric and diamagnetic as expected for their $4d^0$ configuration.

IR spectra : IR spectra of the sulfadruug ligands show medium intensity bands at $3300\text{--}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH). In thiophenethiosemicarbazone strong band appears at $1050\text{--}1040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S). A sharp band at $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N azomethine) is observed in both types of the ligands. On complexation, the band due to ν_{NH} disappears, indicating deprotonation of hydrogen followed by coordination through nitrogen and the band due to $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ also disappears suggesting thioenolisation of the ligand and its chelation with the metal ion through thiol sulfur, respectively. Sharp band due to azomethine moiety shifts slightly towards lower frequency ($10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes, indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom. The bands observed at $3430\text{--}3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$, attributed to asymmetric and symmetric modes of NH_2 group, remain nearly at the same positions in the spectra of the complexes. Some new bands are observed in the complexes at ~ 480 (Mo–N) and $\sim 360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Mo–S). The strong bands exhibited by the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes at $930\text{--}950$ and $900\text{--}915\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to terminal $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$, respectively, of *cis*- MoO_2 configuration, due to the maximum utilization of the available $d\pi$ orbitals for bonding with the oxo group⁴.

¹H NMR spectra : Sulfapyridine and sulfaguanidine ligands show signals at δ 11.75 and 11.80, respectively, due to NH proton which disappear in the complexes showing the deprotonation and the coordination through nitrogen of this group. The presence of two new signals at δ 10.32 and 3.20 in sulfaguanidine ligand show the presence of NH and NH_2 protons, respectively. These signals also appear in the complexes indicating that these are not participating in the coordination. In thiosemicarbazone

ligand, the signal at δ 3.60 (SH) disappears in the complexes, indicating deprotonation and coordination through thiol sulfur.

UV spectra : The ligand bands at ~230 and ~270 nm are due to π - π^* transitions within the benzene ring and that around ~320 nm is due to n - π^* transitions of the azomethine group. However, in the metal complexes the first two bands remain unaltered whereas the third undergoes a blue-shift due to coordination of nitrogen to the central metal atom.

^{13}C NMR spectra : The considerable shift in the positions of carbon atoms adjacent to azomethine nitrogen (155.20–161.62 ppm) and thiolic sulfur (164.15–177.86 ppm) in the ^{13}C NMR spectra further support the proposed coordination in the complexes.

Thermal analyses : Thermogravimetric analyses of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^4)$ have also been carried out to evaluate the thermal stability. The TGA curve for the complex shows first mass loss step from around 96 to 134°. The subsequent step shows mass loss upto 284°. Almost 80% mass loss occurs in both the steps. At 284°, MoO_3 is presumed to be the end product. The compound is stable as the first decomposition starts at 96°.

The DTA profile shows endothermic peaks at 74.7° and 213.7° due to decomposition of the complex. An exothermic peak at $T_{\text{max}} = 493.7^\circ$ corresponds to crystalline phase change.

X-Ray spectral analysis : The X-ray powder diffraction study of the compound $\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^1)$ was carried out (Table 1). The results show that the compound belongs to the orthorhombic crystal system, having unit cell parameters, $a = 30.205 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 14.6868 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 21.8496 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = \sim 90^\circ$.

Biocidal activity : It is evident from the antimicrobial screening data that the metal chelates are more potent than the parent ligands. Sulfaguanidine complexes $\text{Mo}(\text{L})(\text{L}^5)$ and $\text{Mo}(\text{L})(\text{L}^6)$ are more effective among other complexes. The activity of the complexes increases as their concentration increases. The increased potency of metal complexes may be assigned to their increased lipophilic nature arising due to their chelation⁵. Mode of action of antimicrobials may involve various targets in microorganisms e.g. interference with cell wall synthesis, damage to the cytoplasmic membrane as a result of which cell permeability may be attacked or they may disorganise the lipoproteins leading to cell death⁶.

Table 1. X-Ray powder diffraction data of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^1)$

Peak no.	$2\theta(\text{deg.})(\text{obs.})$	h	k	l	d spacing (obs) (\AA)
1	11.5	0	2	2	7.5570
2	12.7	0	0	4	6.8570
3	16.0	0	3	2	5.5350
4	16.7	0	1	5	5.2420
5	23.2	2	3	0	3.8310
6	23.5	2	3	1	3.7830
7	26.8	2	4	1	3.3240
8	28.1	1	1	8	3.1730
9	30.2	3	0	4	2.9500
10	33.7	3	3	4	2.6570
11	36.6	4	0	1	2.4530
12	38.9	4	0	4	2.3130
13	40.4	4	7	3	2.2310
14	46.5	4	2	8	1.9510
15	50.0	0	8	9	1.8230

Table 2. Analytical and physical data of unsymmetrical molybdenum(VI) complexes

Compd.*	Colour	M.p.	Elemental analysis (%)		
			Found (Calcd.)		
			N	S	Mo
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^1)$	Brown	75	11.67 (11.80)	13.38 (13.50)	13.31 (13.40)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^2)$	Light brown	120	12.42 (12.58)	19.08 (19.19)	14.11 (14.28)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^3)$	Brown	117	12.62 (12.85)	19.54 (19.60)	14.28 (14.59)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^4)$	Light brown	135	12.32 (12.61)	14.24 (14.44)	14.11 (14.32)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^5)$	Dark brown	155	14.28 (14.48)	14.01 (14.20)	13.86 (14.10)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})(\text{L}^6)$	Dark brown	150	15.26 (15.49)	20.11 (20.26)	14.92 (15.08)

*LH = Thiophenethiosemicarbazone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$), L^1H = 2-acetylnaphthalene sulfapyridine ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$), L^2H = 2-acetylthiophene sulfapyridine ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$), L^3H = thiophene-2-carbaldehyde sulfapyridine ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$), L^4H = 2-fluorobenzaldehyde sulfapyridine ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2\text{F}$), L^5H = 2-acetylnaphthalene sulfaguanidine ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{SO}_2$), L^6H = 2-acetylthiophene sulfaguanidine ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were dried prior to use. Precautions were taken to exclude moisture from the system. Dioxobis(2,4-

pentanedionato)molybdenum(VI) was prepared according to the literature method⁷.

Preparation of the ligands : Thiophene thiosemicarbazone (LH) was prepared by the condensation of thiophene-2-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide. Sulfadrugs azomethines were prepared by the condensation of different sulfadrugs with various aldehydes or ketones. The sulfadrugs azomethines used (L¹H, L²H, L³H and L⁴H) were synthesized by the condensation of sulfapyridine with 2-acetylnaphthalene, 2-acetylthiophene, thiophene-2-carbaldehyde and 2-fluorobenzaldehyde respectively, while L⁵H and L⁶H were prepared by the condensation of sulfaguanidine with 2-acetylnaphthalene and 2-acetylthiophene, respectively. Reactants were taken in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol and the solution was refluxed or stirred for 7-8 h. On cooling the crystals formed were crystallized in the same solvent and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of the complexes : A methanolic solution (50 ml) of dioxobis(2,4-pentanedionato)molybdenum(VI) and the ligands thiophenethiosemicarbazone (LH) and sulfadrug azomethine (L'H) was refluxed for 12-14 h. After the completion of the reaction, the excess solvent was distilled off and the product was dried *in vacuo* (Table 2).

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CHCl₃) on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a JEOL FX-90Q spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and ¹³C NMR spectra (MeOH) at 22.49

MHz. N and S were estimated by Kjeldahl's and Messenger's methods, respectively. Molecular weights were determined⁸ by the Rast camphor method. Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically⁹ as bis(8-hydroxyquinolato)dioxomolybdenum(VI).

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